

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and
Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**First call for projects in Service 2
Milestone M4.2**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.2

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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zenodo

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M4.2

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Achieved:

Yes

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Comments:

The call for proposals for ESiWACE3 Service 2 has been uploaded to the ESiWACE website on January 31st, 2024. It is publicly accessible under the following URL: <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/software-support/service-calls>

Call for services of type 2

Home / Services / Service Calls / Service2

The "Services on state-of-the-art development tools for Weather and Climate" is now open.

The ESiWACE3 Consortium has just published a "Call for proposals" to apply for some of the services provided by the third phase of ESiWACE - Center of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe. This call aims to support the exascale preparations for the European ESM community.

The call is open to all groups developing and maintaining ESM codes, not only the ESiWACE3 partners.

With this service, the ESiWACE3 Consortium expects to establish collaborative projects in which the ESiWACE experts provide advice and engineering effort to the applicant. Apart from offering limited engineering time and implementing code modifications, the projects aim to provide guidance and establish knowledge transfer between HPC experts and modelling groups.

The description and more details of the call can be found [here \(PDF\)](#).

Please prepare the application following the instructions included in the call and then **submit it using our [online form](#)**.